

F·A·A·M facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. B396
 Date: 19 Aug 2008
 Take Off: 12:25:32Z
 Landing: 17:34:01Z
 Flight Time 5h 08m 29s

Campaign: CAVIAR

Operating Area: Camborne

POB	Position	Name	Institute	Logs y/n
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight	
2	Co-pilot	Luc Lathouwers	Directflight	
3	CCM1	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight	
4	Mission Scientist	Dave Pollard	Met Office	
5	Flight Manager	Mo Smith	FAAM	
6	Cloud Physics / AVAPS / CCM2	Jamie Trembath	FAAM	
7	ARIES / MARSS / DEIMOS	Stuart Newman	Met Office	
8	SWS / SHIMS	Martin Glew	Met Office	
9	CVI / FWVS	Jeff Norwood-Brown	Met Office	
10	TAFTS 1	Paul Green	Imperial College	
11	TAFTS 2	Ralph Beeby	Imperial College	
12				
13				
14				
15				
16				
17				
18				

Flight Track:

B396 Track 19-AUG-08

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B396
 Date: 19 August 2008
 Project: CAVIAR
 Location: Camborne

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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114213		Start-Up	0.68 kft	000	52'04.36N, 0'37.48W
121702		ASP	0.67 kft	051	Already open!
122532		T/O	1.4 kft	022	Cranfield
123431		Event	10.0 kft	238	Zero JW & Nevz
131917	132927	Run 1	20.0 kft	276	A-B
131949		Sonde	20.0 kft	287	Launch #01
132451		Sonde	20.0 kft	286	Launch #02 Data from 800hPa
133530	134551	Run 2	15.0 kft	102	B-A
134152		Sonde	15.0 kft	104	Launch #03
134529		Sonde	15.0 kft	105	Launch #04
135501	140502	Run 3	10.0 kft	288	A-B
140019		Event	10.0 kft	287	Camborne
141033	142035	Run 4	6.5 kft	102	B-A
142929	143931	Run 5	4.0 kft	285	A-B
143506		Event	4.0 kft	285	Ovhd Camborne
144239	145156	Run 6	2.9 - 2.8 kft	109	B-A, QNH 1001hPa
144715		Event	2.8 kft	106	Ovhd Camborne
145412	150019	Run 6.2	2.8 kft	259	A-B,
145942		Event	2.8 kft	287	Ovhd Camborne
150020	150426	Profile 1	2.8 - 0.17 kft	287	2.5k-50', QNH1010
150444	150755	Run 7	0.23 kft	286	100'
150531		Heimann	0.24 kft	285	Cal
150805	151254	Profile 2	0.27 - 5.0 kft	287	From 100'
151608	152423	Run 8	5.0 kft	105	Above cloud
151948		Event	5.0 kft	105	Ovhd Camborne
152851	153852	Run 9	7.0 kft	291	A-B
153430		Event	7.0 kft	285	Ovhd Camborne
154224	155225	Run 10	10.0 kft	124	B-A
154721		Event	10.0 kft	107	Ovhd Camborne
155705	160710	Run 11	14.9 - 15.0 kft	279	A-B
155715		Sonde	15.0 kft	284	Launch #05
160137		Sonde	15.0 kft	286	Launch #06
161738	162737	Run 12	25.0 kft	103	B-A
162215		Sonde	25.0 kft	105	Launch #07
162409		Event	25.0 kft	103	Ovhd Camborne
162519		Sonde	25.0 kft	104	Launch #08, no GPS
163734	164736	Run 13	32.0 kft	285	A-B
163834		Sonde	32.0 kft	285	Launch #09
164335		Sonde	32.0 kft	286	Launch #10
173401		Land	0.63 kft	259	Cranfield
173705		ASP	0.62 kft	307	Closed
173828		Shutdown	0.62 kft	307	52'04.36N, 0'37.50W

B396 Track 19-AUG-08

CAVIAR water vapour continuum flight B396

Take off: 1330L (1230Z)

Location: Cornish peninsula in vicinity of Camborne radiosonde station. Straight and level runs should be conducted partially over sea and partially over land, intercepting the location of the ground station during the run.

Weather conditions: Clear sky (or very nearly clear sky) from surface to space

Important instruments: ARIES, TAFTS, SWS, MARSS, DEIMOS, AVAPS, all water vapour instruments, core chemistry, PCASP

Sortie aim: to sample intensively the water vapour structure of the atmosphere in the area around Camborne, and measure the radiative signature of the water vapour continuum.

Coordinates: aim to fly straight and level runs between fixed coordinates

A = °N, °W

B = °N, °W

The runs are nominally of 10 mins duration, but in practice these will be of longer (shorter) duration at minimum (maximum) altitude.

Radiometers: ARIES and TAFTS to coordinate their upward and downward views during the straight and level runs.

Note that the exact selection of flight altitudes will be made by the mission scientist, depending on the humidity structure of the atmosphere for each flight. In general, it is most useful to concentrate flight levels where the humidity is highest.

Camborne radiosonde ascent: an extra balloon launch has been requested for **1500Z**. Communications between the aircraft and the ground will be made via satellite phone.

Contingency: If conditions are cloudier than CAVIAR requires then FAAM 146 will conduct VACAR science in presence of stratiform/broken cloud.

Sortie items – flight levels are examples only

1. Take off from Cranfield ~**1230Z** and transit to area of operations around Camborne. Arrive at intermediate altitude conducive to fuel economy, e.g. FL200. (45 min)
2. Perform straight and level run (SLR) at FL200 between A and B, dropping two sondes (10 mins, 57 total)
3. Descend in the turn to FL150, rate of descent 1000 ft/min (7 mins, 64 total)
4. Perform SLR (B to A) at FL150, dropping two sondes (10 mins, 74 total)
5. Descend in the turn to FL100, rate of descent 1000 ft/min (7 mins, 81 total)
6. Perform SLR (A to B) at FL100 (10 mins, 91 total)
7. Descend in the turn to FL075, rate of descent 1000 ft/min (5 mins, 96 total)
8. Perform SLR (B to A) at FL075 (10 mins, 106 total)
9. Descend in the turn to FL050, rate of descent 1000 ft/min (5 mins, 111 total)
10. Perform SLR (A to B) at FL050 (10 mins, 121 total)
11. Descend in the turn to FL025, rate of descent 500 ft/min (7 mins, 128 total)
12. Perform SLR (B to A) at FL025 (10 mins, 138 total)
13. Descend in the turn to 50 feet over the ocean, rate of descent 500 ft/min (7 mins, 145 total)
14. Perform SLR (A to B) at minimum permitted altitude (100 feet over ocean, interrupted by profile ascent to minimum altitude over land) (15 mins, 160 total). **Radiosonde balloon launch around this time (1500Z)**
15. Ascend in the turn to FL025, rate of ascent 500 ft/min (7 mins, 167 total)
16. Perform SLR (B to A) at FL025 (10 mins, 177 total)
17. Ascend in the turn to FL040, rate of ascent 500 ft/min (6 mins, 183 total)
18. Perform SLR (A to B) at FL040 (10 mins, 193 total)
19. Ascend in the turn to FL070, rate of ascent 500 ft/min (8 mins, 201 total)
20. Perform SLR (B to A) at FL070 (10 mins, 211 total)
21. Ascend in the turn to FL100, rate of ascent 1000 ft/min (6 mins, 217 total)
22. Perform SLR (A to B) at FL100 (10 mins, 227 total)
23. Ascend in the turn to FL150, rate of ascent 1000 ft/min (7 mins, 234 total)
24. Perform SLR (B to A) at FL150, dropping two sondes (10 mins, 244 total)
25. Ascend in the turn to FL250, rate of ascent 1000 ft/min (12 mins, 256 total)
26. Perform SLR (A to B) at FL250, dropping two sondes (10 mins, 266 total)
27. Ascend in the turn to FL320, rate of ascent 1000 ft/min (10 mins, 276 total)
28. Perform SLR (B to A) at FL320, dropping two sondes (10 mins, 286 total)
29. End of science; transit back to Cranfield (45 mins, total sortie time 331 mins)

Contingency if boundary layer cloud is too thick for CAVIAR: perform VACAR science comprising runs 1000 feet below and above cloud, with saw tooth profiles between these altitudes. Profile to max. altitude and perform run, dropping sondes.

B396 Mission Scientist's Debrief
David Pollard

B396 was a Caviar sortie, conducted over the Camborne upper air station.

The meteorological situation was a north westerly flow over the Cornish peninsula containing various cloud banks. The airmass was unstable to land surface temperatures over the peninsula causing Cu convection to the south west of Camborne.

The sortie was conducted at various levels on a track originating at a point A, situated at 50.08N, 4.51W, and extending NW, over Camborne to give a run time of approximately 10 mins, to end at a nominal position B.

On arrival in the area at 13:20Z there was extensive, broken cloud over the peninsula, with clear skies to the NW. A run was conducted at FL200 (A-B), dropping a sonde at the start and overhead Camborne, followed by another run at FL150 (B-A) with a further two sondes. Further runs at FL065 (A-B), FL040 (B-A) and FL025 (B-A) were conducted, all of which experienced Cu at the SW'ern end (tops at ~4 kft, bases not reached), clear skies over the Camborne site, and the encroachment of a St layer. The St layer had impinged on the flight track by the time of the FL040 run (R5 14:29:29 – 14:39:31Z) which was just in the tops. The descent at the end of this run showed that the St layer was only ~200 ft thick.

This was followed by a low level run from A-B, although it was necessary to start this at FL025, the MSA over land, and conduct a profile descent to 50 ft when safe, followed by a short run at 100 ft. The first part of this run was through Cu, followed by a narrow clear slot over Camborne and then under St. A radiosonde was launched from Camborne during this run at 15:05Z

After this, it was decided to forego the remaining low level work, and concentrate on working above the cloud, so a profile ascent was made to FL050, just above the St at the NW'ern extent of the area, followed by runs at FL050 (B-A), FL070 (A-B), FL100 (B-A), FL150 (A-B), FL250 (B-A) and FL320 (A-B). During the first of these runs, it was apparent that the St was now overlapping with the Cu over the peninsula and these conditions persisted for the remainder of the flight. During the last three runs, 2 dropsondes were released per run. The last two of these and the aircraft sounding, revealed a moist layer at 320 hPa with a significant dry layer between 400 and 500 hPa.

At the end of the run at FL320 it was necessary to recover to Cranfield in order to arrive before the airfield closed.

Mission Scientist's Log

DigiMemo e-Page

Flight No **B.396**... Date **19/8/8**..... Name **P. Pollard**..... Page **1** of **5**...

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
12:26:37					T/O
12:48		140ft			Initial ascent to 100ft quite moist drying in transit, further ascent drier
12:49		180			Moist Layer, quite thin over 8/8 Ac, Sc
12:52		200			end of climb, moist patch as we head to BCN
13:06					1200 SCT 1000 St. Marys BK 1500
13:10		200			Aries has sorted out scripts SHWS ok FWWS & dodgy CWL good TAFIS behaving
13:19:17	R1 289	200	280	1A	SCT Cu all over peninsula fairly broken below more extensive to E Clearance ahead Some Ci, Cs around
13:24					C/H comboune
13:28					4/4 - 2/4 in 10FC

Mission Scientist's Log

DigiMemo e-Page

Flight No **B.39C** Date 19/8/8 Name Volmar Page 2 of 5

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					Problem w/ launch det on sonde 2 sends ok now
13:28					Definite clearing to NW
13:29:22	1	200		B	end
		150			in turn
13:35:30	2	150	100	A	Start A-B
					Close streets below on SE edge
13:41:52					Sonde 3
13:44					streets fade out to SE of peninsula to give clear cond's
13:45:51	2	150			End
13:44					Moistening in this descent
13:51					quite a few legs
13:55:01	3	100	280		A-B
14:00:20					Off Camborne
					Looking clearer on this run
					Some cu w/ st above to NW of B
14:05:02	3	100			end
					Clear cu
14:10:33	4	65	101		B-A
					Very clear below
14:16					going over lee edge

Mission Scientist's Log

DigiMemo e-Page

Flight No **B.396** Date 19/6/8 Name Polunski Page 3 of 5

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
14:20:35	4			10x	End
14:23		~ 4.5hgt			Thru some Cu tops
14:24		4			in cu tops again
14:25					in and out of tops
14:29:20	5	FL40	284	A	A-B
					in a nice moist bit of Cu
14:36					Cld encroaching onto NW end of track
14:37:30					in tops of St/Sc ab NW end of run
14:38:50					Just out of tops
14:39:31	5	FL40			End
14:40		FL38			Just below Sc/St
14:42:39	6	2500ft			B-D under St deck
14:46					Coming out from under St deck
14:46:30					Thin finger of St
14:47:50					into Cu
14:51:25					out of Cu
14:51:58	6				End at a not quite 10min
14:54:12	6.2	2500			Turning onto recip
14:56:37					in Cu
14:58					out of cu, still some
14:59:10					below
					under St
15:00:20	6.2/7.1	500ft			

Mission Scientist's Log

DigiMemo e-Page

Flight No **B.396** Date 19/8/8 Name Pollock Page 4 of 5

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
15:04:25	P1	50			
15:04:44	P7	100	290		Under St
					Heiman Ckt
15:08:05	P2	↑ 425			going up to look at cloud conditions
		FL 42			in cloud base
		FL 46			thin tops
15:12:54	P2	FL 50			above St deck
					looks quite extensive
15:16:08	R9	FL 50			Edge of St deck appears to run W-S
					lovely and clear above
15:18:30					St deck breaking up
					Can believe it
15:24:23	R8	FL 50	100	A	end
					Some thin Ci around
15:28:51	R9	FL 70	291		A-B
15:31:15					Under thin Ci
					Very consistent cirrus for NW'en leg of run
15:38:52	R9				end
15:42:24	R10	FL 100			B-A
15:52:25	R10	"			end climb on turn to 150
15:57:05	"	150	283	A	A-B
					Thin Cs above (maybe)

Mission Scientist's Log

DigiMemo e-Page

Flight No **B**..... Date

Name

Page 5 of 5

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					@ 16:30 z Comb hard
					2/3 St @ 1hgt
					6/8 SL @ 3700ft
16:07:10	11	FL150			End @ B climb to FL250
16:12:38	12	FL250	101	Bish	B-A
					Still have low low St/cu
					seems clear around and above
16:25:10					Some Ci to NE
					Pass than stuff above
16:27:37	12				End @ A climbing in turn to
					FL320
16:37					Ci to SW extending over track
16:37:34	13	320			A-B
					V. low water vapour
					and 1 to MANS3
16:42:36					End of run, end of Science
					Sondes from last run show
					moist layer at 520 mb
					drying right out below
					also on Fd
					Inst status
					THFTs on lower level 1/2
					FWUS odd data, CUI ok
					Arise - ok, MANS3, ok, Weimas
					suspect,

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B396 **T/O:** 122638
Date of flight: 19/08/08 **Land:** 173436

A) FFSSP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer *.txt files from DVD to processing PC Bnnn_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data Bnnn_FFSSP_HVMS.txt		hh = Last sec processed =
2) FTP the files (ascii) from the PC to directory PMSDATA: on FLOODS		File size =
3) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_EXTRACT_TAS a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Path name: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX c) Output directory: PMSDATA: d) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (see comment box)</i> e) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>		Use time just before/after take-off/landing. If T/O /landing just after/before the hour, ensure start/end time is before/after the hour if there is an FFSSP_hh.txt file for that hour.
4) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_PROCESS_TXT a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) TAS in processing: Y d) Vel threshold (clicks) 0 e) Calibration file: <i>Use the most recent calibration file.</i> Format FFSSP_CALddmmyyyy.txt Calibration files to be stored in MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP] f) Adjust FFSSP time Y/N g) If Y, enter value to add to data time (seconds)		Total glitches = Sec file written ok? Note calibration file used Yes only if gross errors occur in FFSSP time eg; ~ 1hour
5) FLOODS> WAVE a) WAVE> write procffssp_to_m5,'pmsdata:Bnnn_procffssp.dat', 'mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX','pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp',/auto b) WAVE> exit		Use PVWAVE for this section Note time correction applied to FFSSP by /auto =
6) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY (y=x+1) d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>		Input file size = M5 output file size =
7) CHECKS: i). Are FFSSP and JW/Nevzorov LWC synchronized in time? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>JW LWC para 535</i> <i>Nevzorov LWC para 602</i> <i>FFSSP LWC para 1202</i> ii). If not, repeat from step 5b replacing /auto with addt=x which adds x+20 secs to FFSSP time.		Synchronized?

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B396 **T/O:** 122638
Date of flight: 19/08/08 **Land:** 173436

B) 2D PROCESSING		REPROCESS +1hr
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer Bnnn.dat file from CD/DVD to PC	Y	
2) Zip up file on PC (Bnnn.zip)	Y	
3) FTP the zipped file (binary) from the PC to the directory SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] on FLOODS	Y	Blocks 12983
4) Log on to FLOODS		
5) Unzip SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.zip	Y	Size of Bnnn.dat = 170318
6) FLOODS> WAVE WAVE> CONVERT_SEADAS_FILE a) Input file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.dat b) Output file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn_seadas.dat WAVE> exit	Y	Use PVWAVE for this section Blocks read = 45714 Blocks written = 45714 Bad reads = 0
7) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SEADAS]READM200_FILE a) Default directory: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Disk file name: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn_seadas.dat d) Comment string: e) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O – 5 min)</i> f) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land + 5 min)</i> g) Read 2DC: Y h) Read 2DP: Y i) Secondary data: Y j) FSP-SYNC: Y k) cmd.str: Y l) Auto time correction: N m) Full length secondary: N	Y	Start = 122638 End = 173436 Ignore error message scroll (vestigial error from tapes) Are FRW, FSP, IMB, PCA,SEC files in PMSDATA - Yes Are they non-zero in size - Y
8) FLOODS> WAVE i). WAVE> imagedisplay a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) File generation no: 0 d) Time from IWC plot: N e) Select probe: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP f) Start time: <i>As in 7e above</i> g) End time: <i>As in 7f above</i> h) Time interval (sec): 5 recommended (0 for all images) ii). WAVE> auto_image a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Enter date: YYYYMMDD d) Enter start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O – 1 min)</i> e) Enter end time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 1 min)</i> f) Enter time interval (sec) between successive imaged blocks: 10 iii). WAVE> exit to create files iv). FTP ascii *.PS files from PMSDATA: to PC v). Load each into Ghostview or other pdf-converter vi). Output as pdf file (720 dpi resolution), appending name prefix of	Y	2D image display and printing Must be done from FLOODS itself. Note any problems with images 2dc fine till 16:50ish then noise (see in flight log) – rain drops 2dp – Not fitted Prepare imagery for Core data From own PC again Start = 122638 End = 173436 FAAM_YYYYMMDD_R0_ Bnnn_2Dx-images.ps Notes on this in instructions 2dc 133 pages

CORE-CLOUD-PHY_ to converted files		2dp 46 pages to 103000
9) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SPEC2D.AUTO]PROCESS2D_AUTO	Y	NB. an error message may appear, floating point exception, rerun and use time quoted in error message, repeat until successful. X = b327_tas
a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) File generation: <i>Hit enter</i> d) Time correction: <i>Time offset of the 2D data</i> e) TAS: Y f) MFD directory: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX g) Probe number: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP (0) Both <i>0 unless either probe known to be faulty</i> h) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O + 30sec)</i> i) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 30sec)</i> j) Nominal averaging: 0.2 seconds for conversion to M5 k) Particle type 2DC: 8 if known to be in ice cloud 11 if known to be in water cloud l) Particle type 2DP: 8 if known to be in mixed-phase 8 if unknown m) Coefficient choice: 2 n) Output root filename: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROC2D		Start = 122638 End = 173436 Time data processed to = 171527 2dproc files present? Y *.2dc, *.2dp and *.dat
10) FLOODS> WAVE	Y	Use PVWAVE for this section
i) WAVE> WRITE_PROC2D_TO_M5, 'PMSDATA:BNNN_PROC2D.DAT', 'PMSDATA:BNNN_M5PROC2D' ii). exit		Error message about HDDR file should be ignored. Records = 16971, 178
11) FLOODS> MODIFY	Y	
a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5proc2D b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default		X = b327_tas Y = (X+1) = b327_tas_2d
12) CHECKS: Are 2DC/2DP IWC of comparable magnitude and well-correlated with Nevzorov TWC? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Nevzerov TWC para 605</i> <i>2DC IWC para 1302</i> <i>2DP IWC para 1312</i>	N	Data present in mfd file Correlated?

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B396 **T/O:** 122638
Date of flight: 19/08/08 **Land:** 173436

C) PCASP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Complete stage 7) in 2D processing Ensures Bnnn_FSP.DAT containing raw PCASP data is written to directory PMSDATA:	Y	
2) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.PCASP]PROCPCASP_NEW a) Flight number: Bnnn b) File name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_FSP.DAT c) Root output name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP Produces PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.DAT (binary) PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.OUT (ascii) d) Minimum size channel: <i>default = 1</i> <i>If smallest size channel are known to be noisy the value of the highest noise free channel to be entered here</i> e) Calibration volume flow rate: <i>Use the most recent value. (1.15ccs⁻¹ Feb 07)</i> <i>Calibration files to be stored in Exeter</i> <i>Entering zero gives default value = 1.0 cm³s⁻¹</i> f) Time correction: <i>Same value as used in 2D processing stage 9d</i> g) Start time: <i>0 if unknown</i> h) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>	Y	Min size = 1 Vol flow rate = 0.8 091000 142300
3) FLOODS> WAVE i). WAVE> write_procpcasp_to_m5, 'pmsdata:Bnnn_procpcasp.dat', 'pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp' ii). WAVE> exit	Y	Use PVWAVE for this section
4) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>	Y	X = b327_tas_2d Y = X+1 = _tas_2dpcasp
5) CHECKS Are PCASP and JW peaks synchronous? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Neph – total blue scatter.</i> <i>PCASP conc para 1550</i>	N	Data present in mfd file Merged OK?

CVI log

8/19/08 12:39:01 PM All horace data coming in loud and clear
8/19/08 1:35:40 PM Start of run 2
8/19/08 1:55:15 PM start of run 3
8/19/08 2:05:11 PM end of run 3
8/19/08 2:05:14 PM
8/19/08 2:10:48 PM start of run 4 fl065
8/19/08 2:20:44 PM end of run 4
8/19/08 3:42:35 PM Counterflow appears ok though in clear air
8/19/08 3:42:48 PM Start of run 10
8/19/08 4:07:22 PM end of run 11
8/19/08 4:10:27 PM Particularly dry air

ARIES flight log

Flight: B396

page 1 of 3

Date: 19/8/08 Operator(s): S.M. NEWMAN

Res: 1

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes: CAVIAR (Camborne SW England)

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Fit ptrn	Scans	View	Shttr	HBB	CBB	Comments
110400		9.		C	71	31	Test of new macro
110655							Abort (need to re-edit ARIES.CDH.Config)
							ARIES disconnected temporarily
111559		9.N30s		C	71	31	NadirLongRun 30sec script CBB 30coadd *Didn't work * stuck at CBB
112206		6.Z30s		O	71	31	ZenithLongRun 30sec script During taxi
112320							Abort, sticking at CBB
112428		4.Z3min		C	71	31	During T/O
112653							Abort, same problem Restart laptop
113042	Transit	1.CM		C	71	30	As test - same problem
113357							Abort
113357	"	9.					Really 123357 etc.
CLOCK HOUR OUT UP TO THIS POINT							
124501		1.CM					
1246							Aborted: unlick start/stop mode
124635		1.CM		C	71	30	Working!!
124725		1.CM		C	71	31	
124808	Transit	7.N30s		C	71	31	NadirLongRun 30sec script Over Sc
125010							Abort
125035	"	6.Z30s		O	71	31	ZenithLongRun 30sec script * Intend to leave shutter permanently open from now on + Clearish above, poss. thin Ci
125242							Abort
131919	R1	6.Z30s		O	71	30.5	Looks clear above; dropmode over Cu
	FL200						Abort 132406
132424		7.N30s		O	71	30	Clear slot below? Some Cu 1326 DFC $\approx$ 2-4 eighths Cu below

Final cal after end of run

ARIES flight log

Flight: 8396

page 2 of 3

Date: 19/8/08 Operator(s): S.M. NEWMAN

Res: 1

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes: CAVAR (Camborne SW England)

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Fit ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
133533	R2	6.230s		0	71	31	Some Ci above to south
	FL150						Abort 134018
134029	"	7.N30s		0	70	31	Scattered Cu below, over ocean at end
	"						Abort 134618 sl. after end of run
135503	R3	6.230s		0	71	31	Pretty clear above
5953	FL100						Abort
140006	"	7.N30s		0	71	31	Just passing over coast at start;
	"						Some Cu but otherwise quite clear
							Abort 140556 after end of run
141036	FOG5	6.230s		0	71	30	Again pretty clear above
	(R4)						Abort (crash) 141522
141531	"	1.CM		0	71	31	To complete calcs
141645	"	7.N30s		0	71	30	Quite thick Cu below
							Abort 142116 after end of run
142529	R5	6.230s		0	71	30	Actually started before run commenced
	FL040						In cloud at times at 142929
							Out of cloud 143040
							Above BL cloud at 1433
							Abort 143504
143513	"	7.N30s		0	71	31	Largely clear below; in cloud 143730 (tops)
							Abort 143946 just after end of run
144240	R6.1	6.230		0	71	31	Layer cloud above until ~ 1446
	FL025						then cloudy again, clear 144715
							4725 abort
144735	"	7.N30s		0	70	31	Thickish Cu (we're in it)
							Abort 145211 (last few spectra in turn)
145413	R6.2	6.230s		0	71	31	In cloud and/or stratoc layer above
	FL025						150020 descent to 50 ft
							1504 patchy BL cloud above
							Abort 150506
150313	100ft	7.N30s		0	71	31	Run over sea surface
	R7						Abort 150830

Microwave Radiometers FLIGHT LOG		Date	19/08/08	Flight	B396	log pages
Operator(s)	Pollard		Campaign	CAVIAR		
Departure	Cranfield		Arrival	Cranfield		

System start

MARSS

Visual pod inspection						X
Close 3 SSP circuit breakers						X
Close all MARSS circuit breakers						X
FERA on			at time	10:50		
Temperature controller initial temps	Ch16	19.6°C	Ch	19.6°C	Ch18	18.8°C
Temperature controller set points		54°C	17	58°C	-20	40°C
MARSS CPU on			at time	10:53		
Initial target temperatures	Hot	290.8	Cold	291.0		
Target heating						X
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						X
Scanning on (LMD box)			at time	11:03		
Scan indication		Monitor	>		Visual	X

Deimos

Deimos Orientation (Nadir or Zenith)						Z
Close all Deimos circuit breakers						X
Turn on Deimos CPU						X
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						X
Start Deimos Software			at time	10:55		
Initial target temperatures	Hot	290.3	Cold	290.7		
Target heating						X
Scan indication		Monitor	>		Visual	X
Weather	Cloud		Precip			
	Surface		Pressure			
	Other					

System functionality check

(after initial system warmup, approx 1 hour)

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC} = t_{DRS} +$	0	at time	12:12		
Brightness temps 'sensible'						X
Target temps	MARSS:	Hot	344	Cold	295	
	Deimos:	Hot	345	Cold	303	
Channel gains 'sensible'	Ch1 A	Ch3 A	Ch1 B	Ch3 B		
	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)		
		93		92		
	Ch16	Ch17	Ch18	Ch19	Ch20	
	(40-44)	(45-49)	(40-44)	(40-44)	(44-48)	
	40.16	32.82	39.81	40.88	41.90	

Power changeover

Headset on before start		
Listen to engine start sequence	4, 3, 2, 1.	
LMD off (3 switches, bottom to top)		
Exit Deimos Software (x)		
POWER CHANGEOVER		
LMD on (3 switches, top to bottom)	then pushbutton	
Restart Deimos Software		
System running again		at time

Flight #	B396	Date	19/08/08	Operator(s)	Pollard	log page	3	of	3
<i>Time</i>	Run id	Alt/FL	<i>Remarks</i>				Sys		

Data Processing Log		Initials	Date
Flight data copied from MARSS/Deimos PC flash disk to Martian C:\Bxxx\			
Check disc space on flash disk (need >~10 MB free)			
Copy* Martian logged data from to C:\Bxxx\			
Wave processing run and BT files generated			
DQM file generated and uploaded			
NetCDF file generated and uploaded			
C:\Bxxx\ copied to USB drive or CD			
Data processing issues/notes:			

B396_SWS_SHIMS_EventLog.txt

```

11:32:16.50 --- - - - -
11:32:16.50 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
11:32:16.50 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
11:32:16.50 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B396
11:32:16.50 --- - - - -
11:32:25.56 SWS - - - - Telescope motor initialised.
11:32:29.84 SWS -0.0 - - - - Telescope sent to 174.000
11:32:31.50 SWS 173.5 - - - - Telescope stopped.
11:32:33.45 SWS 174.0 - - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
11:32:35.11 SWS -1.4 - - - - Telescope stopped.
11:32:43.68 SWS -6.0 - - - - Telescope sent to 90.000
11:32:44.79 SWS 90.0 - - - - Telescope stopped.
11:33:39.24 SWS - 100 - - - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
11:33:41.44 USH - 100 - - - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
11:33:44.54 LSH - 100 - - - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
11:33:47.65 LSH - - - 10 NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 10ms.
11:33:48.24 LSH - - - 10 NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 10ms.
11:33:51.59 LSH - - 1000 - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 1000ms.
11:33:58.30 USH - - 100 - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 100ms.
11:34:00.75 USH - - - 100 NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 100ms.
11:34:01.86 LSH - - - 1000 NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 1000ms.
11:34:03.84 SWS - - - 10 NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 10ms.
11:34:07.54 SWS - - 100 - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 100ms.
11:34:07.54 SWS - - - 100 NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 100ms.
11:34:09.07 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
11:34:31.49 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
11:34:31.59 USH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
11:34:31.68 LSH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
11:34:38.24 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
11:34:43.52 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:34:43.53 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:34:43.53 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:34:45.00 LSH - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark
measurement.
11:34:45.84 USH - - - - Idling
11:34:45.99 SWS - - - - Idling
11:34:55.26 LSH - - - - Idling
11:34:55.29 LSH - - - - Idling
11:34:56.68 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:34:56.68 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:34:56.69 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:34:58.10 LSH - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark
measurement.
11:34:58.11 SWS - - - - Idling
11:34:58.52 USH - - - - Idling
11:34:58.92 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:34:58.92 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:35:00.35 SWS - - - - Idling
11:35:00.56 USH - - - - Idling
11:35:01.00 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:35:01.00 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:35:02.43 USH - - - - Idling
11:35:02.63 SWS - - - - Idling
11:35:04.85 SWS - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not
Recording!
11:35:06.24 USH - - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not
Recording!
11:35:07.32 LSH - - - - Idling

```

11:35:10.80	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:07:49.39	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:07:49.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:07:50.04	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:07:51.26	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
12:07:56.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:07:56.58	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:07:56.59	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:07:58.01	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
12:07:58.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:07:58.43	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:08:02.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:08:02.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:08:04.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:08:04.44	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:08:05.54	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:08:05.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:08:06.97	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:08:07.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:08:07.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:08:07.88	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:08:07.88	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:08:07.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:08:09.31	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
12:08:09.33	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:08:09.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:08:10.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:08:10.42	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:08:11.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:08:12.07	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:08:12.49	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:08:12.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:08:13.92	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:08:14.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:08:15.34	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:08:15.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:08:16.79	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:08:16.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:08:18.55	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:08:19.85	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:08:19.86	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:08:19.87	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:08:33.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:08:34.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:08:35.55	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:27:53.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:27:53.76	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:27:54.53	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:27:56.68	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
12:28:01.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:28:01.26	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:28:01.28	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:28:02.68	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
12:28:02.70	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:28:03.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:28:06.37	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

12:28:06.37	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:28:07.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:28:08.02	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:28:11.95	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:28:14.70	SWS	89.9	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
12:28:15.82	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
12:28:24.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:28:24.56	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:28:24.57	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:28:25.98	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
12:28:25.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:28:26.41	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:28:35.22	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:28:36.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:28:49.16	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:28:51.11	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:29:01.89	SWS	-	-	40	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 40ms.
12:29:01.90	SWS	-	-	-	40	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 40ms.
12:29:04.58	SWS	-	-	-	40	NIR int.time changed from 40ms to 40ms.
12:29:08.75	SWS	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 40ms to 100ms.
12:29:14.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:29:15.85	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:29:17.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:29:18.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:29:23.45	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:29:24.89	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:29:26.95	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:29:30.90	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:31:17.87	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
12:35:47.66	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
12:35:56.88	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
12:36:23.51	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:36:25.24	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:36:31.64	LSH	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 1000ms to 400ms.
12:36:31.64	LSH	-	-	-	400	NIR int.time changed from 1000ms to 400ms.
12:36:33.37	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:36:34.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
12:36:38.32	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:36:42.58	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:37:00.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:37:02.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:37:03.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:37:05.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:38:03.04	---	-	-	-	-	*** Temp
12:38:03.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
12:38:04.57	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:38:06.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:38:07.61	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:38:09.06	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:38:39.64	---	-	-	-	-	*** Freezer temp 11
12:40:31.65	---	-	-	-	-	***
12:40:59.26	---	-	-	-	-	*** About time not working

12:41:11.02	---	-	-	-	-	*** Time set from HORACE by eye
12:41:12.76	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
12:41:17.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
12:41:23.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not
Recording!						
12:41:24.72	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:41:28.65	SWS	-	-	30	-	VIS int.time changed from 40ms to 30ms.
12:41:31.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:41:33.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:41:34.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:41:39.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not
Recording!						
12:41:40.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:41:41.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:41:43.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:41:44.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:45:01.31	---	-	-	-	-	*** Time set by countdown from flight
manager						
12:45:10.19	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:45:10.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:45:10.25	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:45:12.10	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
12:45:17.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:45:17.31	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:45:17.34	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:45:18.13	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark
measurement.						
12:45:18.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:45:19.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:45:21.98	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:45:23.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:45:23.52	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:45:23.53	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:45:24.34	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark
measurement.						
12:45:24.95	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:45:25.36	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:45:25.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:45:25.73	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:45:27.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:45:27.37	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:45:28.18	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:45:28.47	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:45:28.48	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:45:28.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:51:12.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:51:12.20	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:51:12.29	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:51:12.38	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:51:13.81	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
12:51:17.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:51:17.93	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:51:17.94	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:51:18.78	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark
measurement.						
12:51:19.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:51:19.97	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:51:22.61	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:51:22.61	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:51:22.68	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:51:22.75	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

12:51:24.18	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:51:24.26	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:51:24.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:51:25.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:51:25.86	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:51:26.54	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:51:27.57	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:51:29.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:51:29.02	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:51:29.03	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:56:19.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not
Recording!						
12:56:20.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:56:23.75	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
12:56:25.55	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
12:56:27.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:56:29.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:56:30.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:56:39.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:56:41.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:56:43.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not
Recording!						
12:56:46.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:56:49.04	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
12:56:50.80	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
12:56:55.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:56:57.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:57:00.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:00:51.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not
Recording!						
13:00:55.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:00:59.26	SWS	-	-	-	30	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 30ms.
13:01:02.58	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 30ms to 100ms.
13:01:02.58	SWS	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 30ms to 100ms.
13:01:05.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:01:07.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:01:07.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:01:09.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:01:10.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:02:01.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:02:01.26	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:02:01.30	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:02:01.37	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:02:01.37	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:02:02.99	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
13:02:07.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:02:07.08	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:02:07.09	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:02:07.92	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark
measurement.						
13:02:08.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:02:09.07	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:02:09.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:02:09.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:02:10.81	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:02:10.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:02:11.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:02:11.46	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:02:11.98	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:02:13.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:02:13.35	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling

13:02:15.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:02:15.03	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:02:15.05	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:12:16.75	---	-	-	-	-	*** Keepingbfreezer temp 10-12 deg C
13:12:49.96	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:12:49.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:12:50.17	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:12:52.04	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
13:12:56.49	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:12:56.49	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:12:56.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:12:57.32	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
13:12:57.93	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:12:58.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:12:58.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:12:58.74	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:13:00.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:13:00.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:13:00.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:13:00.73	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:13:01.15	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:13:02.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:13:02.37	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:13:02.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:13:02.82	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:13:02.83	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:13:04.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:13:04.67	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:13:05.65	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:13:05.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:13:07.09	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:13:07.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:13:07.47	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:13:07.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:13:07.86	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:13:07.89	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:13:09.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:13:09.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:13:09.90	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:13:09.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:13:11.34	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:13:11.55	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:13:12.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:13:12.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:13:12.52	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:14:11.36	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:16:33.24	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:16:33.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:16:33.52	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:16:37.34	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:16:37.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:16:37.35	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:16:38.37	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
13:16:38.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:16:38.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:16:40.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:16:40.05	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:16:41.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:16:41.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling

13:16:42.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:16:43.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:16:43.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:16:43.69	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:19:32.52	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
13:19:33.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:19:43.04	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
13:19:45.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:24:44.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:24:44.59	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:24:44.73	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:24:46.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:24:46.42	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:24:46.43	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:24:47.24	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
13:24:47.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:24:48.27	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:24:51.11	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:24:51.22	SWS	-0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 180.000
13:24:52.92	SWS	178.2	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
13:24:55.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:24:55.80	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:24:55.81	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:31:06.58	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:31:06.61	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:31:06.65	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:31:11.15	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
13:31:17.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:31:17.42	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:31:17.45	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:31:18.25	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
13:31:18.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:31:19.28	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:31:22.10	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:31:22.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:31:22.31	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:31:22.32	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:31:23.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:31:24.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:31:24.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:31:24.65	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:31:26.09	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:31:26.29	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:31:26.98	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:31:33.42	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
13:31:35.13	SWS	2.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
13:31:40.57	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
13:31:53.41	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:31:55.62	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:32:14.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:32:24.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:32:24.43	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:32:24.62	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:33:33.58	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:33:33.58	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:33:33.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:34:33.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!

13:34:34.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:34:35.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:34:37.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:34:39.93	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
13:34:40.77	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:34:41.69	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:34:43.14	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:34:47.65	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
13:34:48.80	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:34:49.53	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:34:50.16	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
13:34:53.98	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:35:18.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:35:18.59	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:35:18.61	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:40:43.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
13:40:44.15	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:40:47.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:40:49.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:40:50.99	SWS	-0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 180.000
13:40:52.70	SWS	178.8	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
13:40:56.96	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 180.000
13:40:59.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:41:08.52	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
13:41:09.34	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:41:10.18	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:41:11.64	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:41:12.76	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:41:18.25	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
13:41:19.40	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:41:21.68	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:41:22.31	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
13:41:22.74	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
13:41:26.19	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:41:26.72	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:41:36.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
13:41:46.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
13:41:46.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:41:50.08	SWS	-	-	40	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 40ms.
13:41:50.09	SWS	-	-	-	40	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 40ms.
13:41:51.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:41:53.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:41:56.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:45:50.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:45:50.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:45:50.33	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:46:00.16	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
13:46:03.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:46:03.40	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:46:03.40	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:46:04.04	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.

13:46:04.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:46:05.06	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:46:05.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:46:05.49	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:46:06.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:46:07.14	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:46:07.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:46:07.56	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:46:07.86	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:46:08.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:46:09.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:46:15.26	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
13:46:16.96	SWS	1.2	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
13:46:18.42	SWS	-0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
13:46:29.89	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:46:32.35	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:46:46.25	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
13:46:47.09	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:46:49.07	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
13:46:51.12	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:47:09.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:47:09.48	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:47:09.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:47:10.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:47:10.52	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
13:47:11.14	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:47:14.36	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:49:08.26	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:49:08.27	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:49:08.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:49:09.10	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
13:49:09.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:49:09.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:49:12.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:49:12.28	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:49:12.94	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:49:13.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:49:13.92	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:50:10.99	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:50:11.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:50:11.02	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:50:12.05	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
13:50:12.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:50:12.48	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:50:15.91	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:50:57.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:50:57.44	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:50:57.45	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:50:58.27	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
13:50:58.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:50:59.32	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:51:02.13	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:51:02.73	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 40ms to 100ms.
13:51:02.73	SWS	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 40ms to 100ms.
13:51:04.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

13:51:06.15	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:51:15.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:51:15.76	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:51:15.77	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:51:16.60	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
13:51:17.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:51:17.63	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:51:20.43	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:51:46.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:51:47.00	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:51:47.01	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:52:49.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:52:49.43	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:52:49.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:52:54.84	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
13:52:55.97	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:53:00.42	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
13:53:01.56	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:53:06.49	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:53:06.52	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:53:06.52	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:53:07.32	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
13:53:07.95	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:53:08.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:53:11.16	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:53:13.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:53:13.49	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:53:13.51	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:00:17.90	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:00:17.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:00:18.25	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:00:19.75	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 180.000
14:00:21.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:00:21.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:00:21.27	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:00:21.49	SWS	179.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:00:21.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
14:00:22.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:00:23.14	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:00:23.88	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:00:23.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:00:25.36	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:00:25.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:00:25.71	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:00:25.96	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 180.000
14:00:29.57	SWS	-	-	40	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 40ms.
14:00:29.58	SWS	-	-	-	40	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 40ms.
14:00:31.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:00:32.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:00:33.45	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:00:33.45	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:00:33.47	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:01:03.00	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 180.000
14:05:06.01	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:05:06.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:05:06.19	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling

14:05:08.44	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:05:08.44	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:05:08.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:05:09.49	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
14:05:09.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:05:09.93	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:05:12.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:05:12.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:05:13.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:05:13.37	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:05:13.81	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:05:14.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:05:14.18	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:05:14.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:05:15.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:05:15.64	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:05:18.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:05:27.79	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:05:31.01	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:05:50.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:05:56.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:05:57.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:05:59.30	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:06:00.18	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:06:01.72	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:06:02.85	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:06:11.89	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 40ms to 100ms.
14:06:11.91	SWS	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 40ms to 100ms.
14:06:14.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:06:15.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:06:20.12	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:06:21.58	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:06:22.24	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:06:22.86	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
14:06:26.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:07:42.16	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
14:07:50.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:07:50.92	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:07:50.94	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:07:51.76	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
14:07:52.37	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:07:52.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:07:55.59	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:08:18.35	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
14:08:20.08	SWS	0.7	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:08:21.08	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
14:08:52.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:08:52.43	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:08:52.44	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:08:53.26	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
14:08:53.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:08:54.29	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:08:57.10	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:09:16.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

14:09:16.54	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:09:16.55	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:09:17.37	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
14:09:17.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:09:18.40	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:09:21.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:10:36.70	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:10:36.70	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:10:36.72	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:16:31.20	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:16:31.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:16:31.39	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:16:33.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:16:33.73	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:16:33.74	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:16:34.57	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
14:16:35.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:16:35.62	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:16:36.90	SWS	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 100ms.
14:16:38.41	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:16:39.17	SWS	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 100ms.
14:16:42.19	SWS	-	-	40	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 40ms.
14:16:42.20	SWS	-	-	-	40	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 40ms.
14:16:44.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:16:45.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:16:50.97	SWS	-0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 180.000
14:16:52.69	SWS	179.3	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:16:53.73	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 180.000
14:16:55.52	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:16:55.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:16:55.53	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:20:39.45	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:20:39.46	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:20:39.57	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:20:40.99	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:20:40.99	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:20:41.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:20:41.82	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
14:20:42.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:20:42.44	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:20:43.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:20:43.43	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:20:44.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:20:45.14	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:20:45.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:20:49.76	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 40ms to 100ms.
14:20:49.77	SWS	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 40ms to 100ms.
14:20:51.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:20:53.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:20:59.12	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
14:21:00.84	SWS	0.7	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:21:01.75	SWS	-0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
14:22:58.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:22:58.14	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:22:58.15	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:22:59.30	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
14:23:00.00	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling

14:23:00.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:23:03.14	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:24:45.30	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:24:45.32	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:24:45.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:24:46.15	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
14:24:46.77	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:24:47.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:24:49.98	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:26:46.91	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:26:46.91	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:26:46.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:26:47.54	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
14:26:48.56	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:26:49.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:26:49.76	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:26:49.77	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:26:51.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:26:51.37	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:26:51.44	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:28:27.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:28:27.05	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:28:27.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:28:27.88	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
14:28:28.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:28:28.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:28:29.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:28:29.05	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:28:29.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
14:28:31.72	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:28:36.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
14:28:37.52	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:28:40.79	SWS	-	-	40	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 40ms.
14:28:40.79	SWS	-	-	-	40	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 40ms.
14:28:43.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:28:45.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:28:46.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:29:18.39	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:35:33.29	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:35:33.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:35:33.43	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:35:35.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:35:35.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:35:35.22	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:35:36.04	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
14:35:36.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:35:37.09	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:35:39.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:35:45.97	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 180.000
14:35:47.70	SWS	179.3	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:35:49.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:35:49.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:35:49.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:35:52.16	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 180.000
14:39:35.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:39:35.36	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling

14:39:35.63	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:39:38.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:39:38.81	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:39:38.83	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:39:39.64	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
14:39:39.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:39:40.74	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:39:42.49	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:39:42.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:39:43.47	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:39:43.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:39:44.01	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:39:44.60	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:39:44.60	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:39:44.61	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:39:45.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:39:46.46	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:39:46.85	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:39:46.87	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:39:47.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:39:48.53	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:39:49.25	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:39:55.11	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
14:39:56.83	SWS	0.4	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:39:57.77	SWS	-0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
14:41:42.33	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:41:42.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:41:42.35	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:41:42.97	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
14:41:43.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:41:44.19	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:41:45.96	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:41:45.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:41:46.80	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:41:47.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:41:47.45	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:42:44.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:42:44.52	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:42:44.52	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:47:50.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:47:50.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:47:50.27	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:47:52.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:47:52.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:47:52.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:47:53.07	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
14:47:53.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:47:53.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:47:56.98	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:48:01.92	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 180.000
14:48:03.65	SWS	179.6	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:48:04.78	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 180.000
14:48:07.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:48:07.15	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:48:07.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:52:01.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:52:01.41	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:52:01.45	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling

14:52:17.50	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
14:52:19.23	SWS	0.4	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:52:20.12	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
14:52:24.45	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:52:24.46	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:52:24.47	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:52:25.29	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
14:52:25.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:52:26.33	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:52:29.14	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:54:08.25	---	-	-	-	-	*** Time reset, 3 seconds fast at reset
14:54:14.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:54:14.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:54:14.13	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:00:40.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:00:40.70	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:00:40.95	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:00:41.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:00:41.80	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:00:41.82	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:00:42.63	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
15:00:42.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:00:43.65	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:00:45.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:00:45.33	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:00:46.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:00:46.48	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:00:46.98	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:01:02.58	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:01:02.59	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:01:02.60	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:03:28.73	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:03:28.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:03:28.90	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:03:35.32	SWS	-0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 180.000
15:03:35.65	SWS	10.4	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
15:03:37.69	SWS	10.4	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 180.000
15:03:39.42	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
15:03:42.15	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 180.000
15:03:50.46	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 40ms to 200ms.
15:03:50.47	SWS	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 40ms to 200ms.
15:03:52.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:03:55.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:03:55.93	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:03:55.93	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:03:55.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:05:26.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
15:05:27.70	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:05:30.20	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
15:05:31.93	SWS	0.2	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
15:05:35.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:05:36.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
15:05:38.54	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
15:05:39.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:05:43.61	SWS	-	-	45	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 45ms.
15:05:43.62	SWS	-	-	-	45	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 45ms.
15:05:46.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

15:05:47.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:05:49.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:06:03.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
15:06:07.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:06:10.02	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 45ms to 200ms.
15:06:10.03	SWS	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 45ms to 200ms.
15:06:11.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:06:14.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:06:18.40	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 180.000
15:06:20.13	SWS	179.6	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
15:06:21.60	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 180.000
15:06:24.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:06:27.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:06:27.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:07:59.90	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:07:59.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:08:00.26	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:08:03.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:08:03.32	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:08:03.33	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:08:04.16	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
15:08:05.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:08:05.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:08:06.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:08:06.39	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:08:07.99	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:08:08.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:08:08.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:08:18.28	SWS	180.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
15:08:20.02	SWS	0.4	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
15:08:21.03	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
15:08:26.83	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
15:08:34.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:08:34.29	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:08:34.30	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:08:35.12	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
15:08:36.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:08:36.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:08:37.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:08:37.85	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:08:38.95	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:08:39.51	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:08:40.55	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:12:14.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:12:14.24	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:12:14.28	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:12:15.29	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
15:12:16.29	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:12:17.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:12:19.56	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:12:23.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:12:23.59	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:12:23.61	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:12:24.43	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
15:12:25.45	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:12:26.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling

15:12:26.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:12:26.88	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:12:28.29	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:12:28.57	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:12:29.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:13:20.00	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
15:13:28.51	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
15:13:31.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
15:13:40.04	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 100ms.
15:13:40.06	SWS	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 100ms.
15:13:43.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:13:44.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
15:13:45.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:13:46.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
15:13:48.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:13:50.52	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:13:53.44	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:13:56.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:13:56.51	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:13:56.53	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:13:57.36	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
15:13:57.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:13:58.40	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:14:01.18	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:14:38.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:14:38.70	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:14:38.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:15:45.89	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:15:45.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:15:45.97	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:15:47.54	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:15:47.55	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:15:47.56	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:15:48.47	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
15:15:49.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:15:49.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:15:51.12	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:15:51.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:15:52.34	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:18:47.36	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:21:45.35	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:21:45.37	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:21:45.40	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:21:48.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:21:48.54	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:21:48.55	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:21:49.37	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
15:21:50.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:21:50.41	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:21:52.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:21:52.20	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:21:53.20	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:21:59.02	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

15:24:26.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:24:26.27	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:24:26.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:24:32.79	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:24:34.24	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:24:39.24	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:24:39.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:24:39.26	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:24:39.88	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
15:24:40.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:24:41.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:24:43.73	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:24:43.85	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:24:43.86	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:24:43.88	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:24:45.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:24:45.73	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:24:48.52	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:27:49.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:27:49.80	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:27:49.82	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:27:50.83	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
15:27:51.84	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:27:51.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:27:53.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:27:53.31	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:27:54.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:28:26.74	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:28:27.37	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
15:28:31.20	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:28:34.18	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:34:40.02	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:34:40.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:34:40.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:34:41.66	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
15:34:45.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:34:45.57	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:34:45.59	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:34:46.41	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
15:34:47.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:34:47.42	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:34:47.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:34:47.96	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:34:49.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:34:49.61	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:34:50.25	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:34:51.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:34:51.58	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:34:51.59	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:38:55.91	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:38:55.96	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:38:56.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:38:59.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:38:59.94	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:38:59.94	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:39:00.77	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.

15:39:01.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:39:01.83	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:39:04.60	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:39:06.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:39:06.06	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:39:06.07	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:39:06.90	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
15:39:07.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:39:07.94	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:39:10.72	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:41:10.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:41:10.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:41:10.14	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:41:11.16	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
15:41:11.58	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:41:12.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:41:15.02	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:41:35.38	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:41:35.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:41:35.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:41:36.01	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
15:41:37.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:41:37.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:41:39.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:42:19.53	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:42:19.54	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:42:19.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:42:20.39	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
15:42:21.02	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:42:21.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:42:24.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:42:27.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:42:27.29	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:42:27.31	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:48:45.52	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:48:45.54	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:48:45.88	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:48:47.61	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:48:47.62	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:48:47.63	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:48:48.45	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
15:48:49.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:48:49.52	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:48:50.95	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:48:50.97	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:48:52.33	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:48:52.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:48:52.64	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:48:54.51	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:48:54.51	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:48:54.54	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:52:29.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:52:29.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:52:29.18	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:52:32.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:52:32.11	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

15:52:32.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:52:32.96	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
15:52:33.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:52:33.99	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:52:36.80	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:52:42.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:52:42.19	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:52:42.20	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:52:43.03	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
15:52:43.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:52:44.06	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:52:45.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:52:45.83	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:52:46.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:52:47.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:52:47.52	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:52:48.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:52:48.99	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:52:49.01	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:52:49.83	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
15:52:50.45	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:52:50.87	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:52:51.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:52:51.25	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:52:52.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:52:52.92	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:52:53.68	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:53:44.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:53:44.64	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:53:44.65	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:53:45.47	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
15:53:46.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:53:46.51	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:53:49.32	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:55:15.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:55:15.51	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:55:15.52	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:55:16.35	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
15:55:16.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:55:17.37	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:55:20.19	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:55:48.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:55:48.08	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:55:48.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:55:48.92	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
15:55:49.55	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:55:49.98	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:55:52.75	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:57:09.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:57:09.63	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:57:09.64	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:02:14.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:02:14.84	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:02:14.99	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:02:17.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

16:02:17.09	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:02:17.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:02:17.92	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
16:02:18.60	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:02:18.97	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:02:19.28	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:02:19.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:02:20.75	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:02:20.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:02:22.18	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:02:23.56	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:02:23.57	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:02:23.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:07:13.41	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:07:13.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:07:13.73	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:07:15.67	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:07:15.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:07:15.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:07:16.57	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
16:07:17.19	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:07:17.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:07:18.88	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:07:18.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:07:20.37	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:07:20.41	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:07:20.55	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:09:04.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:09:04.30	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:09:04.31	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:09:05.33	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
16:09:05.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:09:06.36	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:09:07.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:09:07.96	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:09:09.19	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:09:09.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:09:09.63	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:11:03.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:11:03.65	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:11:03.66	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:11:04.49	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
16:11:05.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:11:05.53	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:11:08.32	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:13:59.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:14:05.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
16:14:06.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:14:12.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:14:13.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:14:17.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:14:17.84	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:14:17.87	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:14:19.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
16:14:19.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling

16:14:19.96	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:14:23.07	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:16:00.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:16:01.00	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:16:01.01	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:16:01.84	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
16:16:02.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:16:02.89	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:16:05.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:16:06.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:16:06.42	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:16:06.43	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:16:07.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:16:08.30	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:16:11.08	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:17:35.55	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:17:35.56	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:17:35.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:17:36.40	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
16:17:37.01	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:17:37.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:17:40.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:17:40.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:17:40.95	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:17:40.96	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:20:46.02	SWS	-0.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
16:20:46.47	SWS	2.1	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -45.000
16:20:50.03	SWS	44.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
16:20:50.75	SWS	36.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
16:20:51.53	SWS	28.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
16:20:52.27	SWS	18.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
16:20:52.97	SWS	10.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
16:20:53.73	SWS	1.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
16:20:54.49	SWS	-7.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
16:20:55.25	SWS	-17.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
16:20:56.00	SWS	-26.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
16:20:56.75	SWS	-35.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
16:20:57.51	SWS	-44.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
16:21:05.75	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
16:21:14.00	SWS	-45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
16:21:21.86	SWS	45.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -45.0
16:21:29.64	SWS	-44.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 45.0
16:21:34.17	SWS	5.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
16:21:46.82	SWS	5.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
16:21:50.05	SWS	-0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 0.000
16:22:47.65	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:22:47.70	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:22:47.74	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:22:49.91	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
16:22:53.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:22:53.18	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:22:53.22	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:22:53.94	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:22:54.04	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
16:22:54.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:22:55.43	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:22:56.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:22:56.07	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

16:22:57.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:22:57.74	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:22:57.88	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:22:58.53	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:22:58.54	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:22:58.55	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:23:13.68	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
16:23:14.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:23:20.02	SWS	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 300ms.
16:23:20.03	SWS	-	-	-	300	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 300ms.
16:23:22.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:23:26.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:23:27.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:23:30.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:23:32.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:23:42.94	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
16:23:43.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:23:46.94	USH	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 200ms.
16:23:46.95	USH	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 200ms.
16:23:49.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:23:52.12	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:23:52.45	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:23:54.90	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:23:55.35	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:25:28.29	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
16:25:29.45	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:25:30.55	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:25:31.18	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
16:25:35.03	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:25:36.45	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:27:42.54	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:27:42.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:27:42.63	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:27:45.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:27:45.01	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:27:45.02	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:27:45.85	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
16:27:47.89	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:27:48.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:27:49.70	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:32:15.66	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:32:15.66	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:32:15.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:32:16.31	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
16:32:19.41	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:32:19.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:32:19.52	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:32:19.86	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:32:20.48	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
16:32:22.52	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:32:23.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:32:24.32	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:32:28.42	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:32:28.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:32:30.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

16:32:30.08	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:32:30.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:32:30.92	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
16:32:32.98	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:32:33.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:32:34.80	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:34:53.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:34:53.74	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:34:53.80	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:34:55.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
16:34:55.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:34:57.07	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:34:58.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:34:59.78	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:35:39.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:35:39.68	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:35:39.70	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:35:40.68	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
16:35:41.14	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
16:35:42.99	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:35:43.45	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:35:44.78	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:37:16.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:37:16.71	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:37:16.73	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:37:17.56	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
16:37:19.63	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:37:20.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:37:21.44	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:37:38.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:37:38.16	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:37:38.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:41:14.72	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:41:14.80	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:41:14.86	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:41:17.03	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:41:17.04	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:41:17.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:41:17.88	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
16:41:19.51	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:41:20.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:41:21.77	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:41:22.43	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:41:22.45	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:41:22.45	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:46:32.31	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:46:32.33	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:46:32.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:46:33.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:46:33.59	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:46:33.62	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:46:34.44	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
16:46:36.55	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:46:37.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling

16:46:38.32	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:46:38.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:46:38.78	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:46:38.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:48:21.67	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:48:21.81	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:48:21.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:48:26.66	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:48:26.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:48:26.68	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:48:27.51	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark
measurement.						
16:48:29.14	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:48:29.98	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:48:30.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:48:31.39	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:48:32.49	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:48:37.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:48:37.94	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:48:37.98	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:48:38.79	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark
measurement.						
16:48:40.90	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:48:41.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:48:43.14	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:48:43.16	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:48:46.78	---	-	-	-	-	*** endex

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B396

Date: 19/08/08

Instruments

1. Satcom C – pre-flight turnaround message “Issue Failed”. Resubmitted it then okay.
2. HORACE – H_Time crashing continuously with “subscript 1 range error”. Restarted process, then okay.
3. ASPs – went to open them on pre T/O taxi, already open
4. FAAM Camera – not onboard aircraft
5. Sondes – Launch detect problem on Sonde #02
6. Chem DLU – From Option 7, DRS Control Menu, Type 4 messages being collected (as standard) but T4 incrementing whereas all other DLUS have T2 messages. Reset DLU CB then CoreChem DLU incrementing T2 messages
7. TAFTS laser worked for about ½ the flight.
8. Cloud Physics- 2DC noisy in transit. CPI, CAPS, SID2 not operated.
9. AVAPS – Sonde 02, launch detect pin error, Sonde 08, no gps data (winds)
10. FWVS – problems initially in that lamp not coming on at DP = -21C. Computer locked up. Restarted then okay. Running in manual as not receiving HORACE GE data.
11. MARSS - okay / DEIMOS – monitoring software crashed but otherwise okay. DEIMOS data still suspect

12. SWS / SHIMS – Okay, CVI – good, ARIES - okay

Aircraft

Nil

ISDN Emails

Nil

MPDS

1 x email – FAAM

3 x Satpics - CAVIAR

Satcom-H Calls

1 - CAVIAR

Issues

Nil

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by

Flight:

B396

KEY

Not Fitted

Fitted, Not Operated

Duff Data

Minor Problems

OK

Thermometers

Cabin Temperature:

Heimann:

Deiced Temp:

Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

FWVS:

Buck CR2:

General Eastern:

Johnson Williams:

Nezvorov:

Total Water Probe:

Cameras

Downward Facing:

Forward Facing:

Rearward Facing:

Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

Cruciform GPS:

GIN Applanix:

INU Honeywell:

Radar Altimeter:

RVSM IAS:

RVSM Static Pressure:

XR5 GPS:

Misc Core

AMTG:

AVAPS:

Cabin Pressure:

Fax machine:

Printer:

S9 Static Pressure:

Satcom C:

Satcom H:

Turb Centre-Static:

Turb Left Right:

Turb Up-Down:

Turb Horizontal Chk:

Turb Vertical Chk:

Weather Radar:

DLUs:

DLU AERACK:

DLU BBR Lower:

DLU BBR Upper:

DLU Core Chem:

DLU Core Consoles:

DLU Port Aft:

DLU Port Fwd:

DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

Lower:

BBR (clear) Lower:

BBR (IR) Lower:

BBR (red) Lower:

Upper:

BBR (clear) Upper:

BBR (IR) Upper:

BBR (red) Upper:

ARIES:

DEIMOS:

IR Camera:

JNO2 Lower:

JNO2 Upper:

JO1D Lower:

JO1D Upper:

MARSS:

SHIMS Lower:

SHIMS Upper:

SWS:

TAFTS:

Cloud Probes

2DC:

2DP:

FFSSP:

PCASP:

2DS:

ADA:

CAPS:

CCN:

CDP:

CIP 100:

CIP 25:

CPI:

CVI:

SID1:

SID2:

Aerosol

CPC 3025A:

CPC 3786 H2O:

Filters 47mm:

Filters 90mm:

Neph - Dry:

Neph - Wet:

PSAP:

AMS:

CPC 3025 (AMS)

INC:

VACC:

CPC 3010A (CVI):

SP2:

UHSAS:

Chemistry

CO Aerolaser 5002:

NOx TE42C:

Ozone TE49C:

Ozone TE49:

SO2 TE43C:

TDLAS (NIR) CH4:

TDLAS (NIR) CO2:

FAGE:

Formaldehyde:

NOx FAAM:

NOxy:

ORAC:

PAN:

PERCA:

Peroxide:

PTRMS:

TDLAS (1C):

WAS Bags:

WAS Bottles:

Misc Non-Core

CASI/ATM:

LIDAR:

LTI:

SAW Hygrometer:

Pre-Flighter's Log

Date: 19/8/08

Flight No: B 396

Pre-Flighter: *Am*

No.	✓ or x	Location	Action	Comments
1	☒	Hangar	Collect spanners for core chem	
Aircraft Cabin: Power-up				
2	☒	Core Chemistry	Gases x 3 ON	
3	☒	Cabin	All Racks Checked	
4	☒	Core Chemistry	Instruments Checked OK	
5	☒	Core Chemistry	CO Flows Checked OK	
6	☒	Aft CorCon	All reqd CBs made	
7	☒	Fore CorCon	CBs made, PCs ON	
8	☒	HORACE	Optical Disk loaded	
9	☒	HORACE	Recording data	
10	☒	HORACE	DLU Status Checked	
11	☒	HORACE	HORACE Status Checked	
12	☒	Satcom H	Power LED ON	
13	☒	Nevzorov	Checked and OFF	
14	☒	Cameras Pictures	Checked x 4 OK	
15	☒	Video Laptop	Checked onboard	
16	☒	FWVS	Set up & check on AUTO	
17	☒	Delced Rosemount	Heater Checked then OFF	
18	☒	Heimann	Calibration Checked	
19	☒	TWC	Fitted & signals checked	
20	☒	GE	Balance checked then back to DP	
21	☒	GPS (XR5M)	Checked	
22	☒	Satcom C	Checked	
23	☒	Video x 2	Records okay, Rewind	

No.	✓ or x	Location	Action	Comments
24	☒	Miss. Sci Laptop	Checked Onboard	In cockpit
25	☒	CNC	Butanol filled	
26	☒	Dry Neph	Power up & Zero Cal	
27	☒	PSAP	Pre-flight log actions complete	
28	☒	CGPS	CBs and PC ON	
External Checks				
29	☒	Turb Probe	Clean if reqd, Photo taken	<i>NO PHOTO</i>
30	☒	JW	Cleaned & Checked	
31	☒	DI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
32	☒	NDI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
33	☒	Nevzorov	Cleaned/windings checked	
34	☒	GE	Cleaned & Checked	
35	☒	Lower BBRs	Domes cleaned/checked	
36	☒	Camera Windows	Cleaned	
37	☒	Heimann	Lens checked OK	
38	☒	TWC Cover	Fitted if required	
39	☒	All other covers	Removed	
40	☒	Pre-flight Bag	Returned to hold	** Check no butanol** ✓
41	☐	Tools	Check ALL in Toolkit	
42	☐	Tools	Avalon informed	
Avalon Checks				
44	☐	Upper BBRs Checked & Cleaned		<u>Signed</u>
45	☐	ICEX applied		
46	☐	Turb Probe - Traps emptied, detail contents -		a)Nil b)1-2 drops c)1/4 full or more
47	☐	Turb Probe - Traps dried and resealed		

EIEA11 MSG 3.9 micron Infrared Image 19 Aug 2008 1400 UTC

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B396:

Log	Reason
Core Chemistry / TDLAS	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
TAFTS	operator does not create a log sheet
FWVS	operator does not create a log sheet

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	10 Dec 2008	Doug Anderson	Initial version
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

The following video recordings in avi format should be available at the BADC :

faam-video-dfc_faam_20080819_r0_b396_125818_1hz.avi
faam-video-dfc_faam_20080819_r0_b396_125919_1hz.avi
faam-video-dfc_faam_20080819_r0_b396_135919_1hz.avi
faam-video-dfc_faam_20080819_r0_b396_145919_1hz.avi
faam-video-dfc_faam_20080819_r0_b396_155919_1hz.avi
faam-video-dfc_faam_20080819_r0_b396_165919_1hz.avi

faam-video-ufc_faam_20080819_r0_b396_125815_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20080819_r0_b396_125916_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20080819_r0_b396_135916_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20080819_r0_b396_145916_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20080819_r0_b396_155916_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20080819_r0_b396_165916_1hz.avi

faam-video-rfc_faam_20080819_r0_b396_125914_1hz.avi
faam-video-rfc_faam_20080819_r0_b396_141152_1hz.avi
faam-video-rfc_faam_20080819_r0_b396_151152_1hz.avi
faam-video-rfc_faam_20080819_r0_b396_161152_1hz.avi
faam-video-rfc_faam_20080819_r0_b396_171152_1hz.avi

No Digital8 video recordings were made on this flight.